

Artificial fear for the control of autonomous robots

Andrea Usai

Department of Electronics and Telecommunications
Politecnico di Torino
Torino, Italy
(andrea.usai@polito.it)

Alessandro Rizzo

Department of Electronics and Telecommunications
Politecnico di Torino
Torino, Italy
(alessandro.rizzo@polito.it)

Abstract—We present a neuro-inspired control framework for autonomous robots that integrates an artificial emotion of fear, drawing inspiration from LeDoux’s dual-pathway hypothesis. To replicate the “Low Road” pathway, our system comprises proxies for the thalamus, implemented as a nonlinear filter; the amygdala, modeled as a Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) reinforcement learning agent; the brainstem, orchestrated through a Nonlinear Model Predictive Controller (NMPC). The NMPC’s parameters are adjusted by the amygdala, enabling it to generate control inputs to actuate the robot. Our preliminary results demonstrate that the robot exhibits a better adaptive behavior than a standard NMPC in both static and dynamic environments with obstacles characterized by different hazard levels.

Index Terms—NMPC, reinforcement learning, mobile robots, obstacle avoidance, neuroscience

I. INTRODUCTION AND METHODOLOGY

Survival and self-preservation are crucial for developing intelligent robots that can adapt to dynamic and unknown environments [1]. Implementing artificial emotions, among which fear has been mostly pursued, can help robots to better evaluate and respond to unexpected and potentially dangerous situations [2]. While most approaches incorporate emotions as adaptive mechanisms to enhance human-robot interaction in social contexts [3], few efforts use artificial emotions for autonomous robot control. Here, we take inspiration from neuroscientific evidence to propose a novel implementation of an artificial fear mechanism in robotics, to enhance robot’s self-preservation. The *Dual-pathway hypothesis* is a neuroscientific model developed by Joseph LeDoux [4], which describes how the brain interprets the fear of external stimuli and how this influences the resulting behaviour. LeDoux suggests the presence of two afferent neural pathways involving the amygdala, which work together to mediate the conditioned fear response: the *Low Road* and the *High Road*. The Low Road enacts instinctive and fast reactions to stimuli, whereas the High Road mediates these stimuli with contextual information, past experience and reasoning ability. Based on this model, we present a new fear-based control architecture to enhance

This study was carried out within the FAIR - Future Artificial Intelligence Research and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PNRR – Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.3 – D.D. 1555 11/10/2022, PE00000013). This manuscript reflects only the authors’ views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

robot’s self-preservation. At present, the model only reproduces the Low Road, comprising the amygdala, the thalamus and the brainstem-musculoskeletal system connection (see Fig. 1(a)). Each component is modeled based on its primary functions within the pathway. A brief explanation of each component is provided below:

1) *Thalamus*: It collects, selects, and fuses different types of environmental stimuli and transmits them as raw information to the amygdala. We model it as a filtering function $\Phi(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{x}_k^{\text{env}})$, which takes in input the robot state vector \mathbf{x}_k and the available environment information $\mathbf{x}_k^{\text{env}}$ at the discrete time k to create an observation vector $\mathbf{s}_k = \Phi(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{x}_k^{\text{env}}) = [\varphi_k^{(1)}, \varphi_k^{(2)}, \dots, \varphi_k^{(p)}]^T$ composed of the $p \in \mathbb{N}$ main features $\varphi_k^{(p)}$ that can help the amygdala to assess the situation the robot is facing (e.g. obstacles distances and velocities, etc).

2) *Amygdala*: It evaluates the raw signals coming from the thalamus to identify potential threats by associating them to a negative or positive consequence. This association is achieved by a punishment/reward mechanism that serves to determine the emotional valence of the stimulus [5]. Therefore, we design an artificial fear emotion \mathcal{F}_k whose discrete time behaviour is described by $\mathcal{F}_k = \sigma(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{s}_k)$ where \mathbf{s}_k is the observation state extracted by the thalamus, \mathbf{w}^T is a vector of manually tuned weights and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a sigmoid function. The amygdala augments the observation vector of the thalamus with the current fear value \mathcal{F}_k . At each time k , such an augmented observation vector $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k = [\varphi_k^{(1)}, \varphi_k^{(2)}, \dots, \varphi_k^{(p)}, \mathcal{F}_k]^T$ is used by the amygdala to derive a vector of optimal parameter matrices $\mathbf{a}_k^* = [Q_k, R_k, \alpha_k, \beta_k]^*$ for the NMPC. The latter, which emulates the brainstem, exploits such parameter matrices to actuate the robot motion (i.e., the musculoskeletal system). Such vector is selected over a continuous action space through a reinforcement learning approach based on a Soft Actor-Critic agent. The action selection is guided by a reward function defined as $R(\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_k, \mathbf{a}_k) = R_F + R_I + R_G$ where R_F promotes actions that reduce fear, R_I penalizes actions leading to infeasible states for the NMPC and R_G promotes actions guiding the robot to its goal in the shortest possible time.

3) *NMPC*: As stated above, it receives its parameters from the amygdala, which accounts for the level of fear and other exogenous information. Here, we consider a mobile robot

Fig. 1: a) Fear-based control architecture based on the Low Road – b) Coordinate systems of the mobile robot: $[x_k, y_k]$ and θ_k are the position and the orientation of the robot in the inertial frame $\{O, X, Y\}$, v_k and ω_k are the linear and angular velocity of the robot in the body frame $\{O_B, X_B, Y_B\}$, respectively – c) Comparison of RL-NMPC with a base NMPC in a static environment – d) Comparison of RL-NMPC with a base NMPC in a dynamic environment.

model as a unicycle (Fig. 1(b)), with discrete-time kinematics

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{k+1} \\ y_{k+1} \\ \theta_{k+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_k \\ y_k \\ \theta_k \end{bmatrix} + T_s \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_k & 0 \\ \sin \theta_k & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_k \\ \omega_k \end{bmatrix} = f_d(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_k = [x_k \ y_k \ \theta_k]^T$ and $\mathbf{u}_k = [v_k \ \omega_k]^T$ are the state vector and the control input vector at discrete time instant k , respectively. At each time step k , the amygdala provides parameter matrices Q_k, R_k, α_k and β_k to the NMPC, which computes the optimal control input sequence $\mathbf{u}^*(\cdot|k)$ over the prediction horizon $N \in \mathbb{N}$ by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{u}(\cdot|k)} \quad & \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \ell(\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}, \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}, Q_k, R_k) + B(\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}, \alpha_k, \beta_k) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{x}_{k|k} = \mathbf{x}_k, \\ & \mathbf{x}_{k+i+1|k} = f_d(\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}, \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}), \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, N-1, \\ & \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k} \in \mathbb{U}, \quad \mathbf{x}_{k+i+1|k} \in \mathbb{X}, \quad \forall i = 0, \dots, N-1, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{U} is the set of feasible control inputs and \mathbb{X} is the set of feasible states. The stage cost $\ell(\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}, \mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}, Q_k, R_k) = \|\mathbf{x}_r - C\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}\|_{Q_k}^2 + \|\mathbf{u}_{k+i|k}\|_{R_k}^2$ is intended to guide the robot toward the goal \mathbf{x}_r while the term $B(\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}, \alpha_{k_j}, \beta_{k_j}) = \sum_{j=1}^{n_{obs}} -\alpha_{k_j} \log(\beta_{k_j} \|C\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k} - \mathbf{x}_{obs_j}\|^2)$ is a logarithmic penalty function designed to move the robot away from the j -th harmful environmental obstacle in position \mathbf{x}_{obs_j} . Indeed, to ensure a better adaptive behaviour, the amygdala is able to estimate different logarithmic penalty function parameters α_{k_j} and β_{k_j} according the dangerousness of the j -th obstacles. Finally, the term $C = \text{diag}([1, 1, 0])$ is a matrix that extracts the robot's position from the state vector $\mathbf{x}_{k+i|k}$.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our approach has been validated through MATLAB simulations (see Fig. 1(c) and Fig. 1(d)). Preliminary results indicate that the robot's behavioral response can be modulated according to the fear level, producing better adaptive behavioral response with respect a standard NMPC, in both static and dynamic environments with different type of hazardous

obstacles. Furthermore, our proposed approach provides two key advantages compared to a conventional NMPC implementation. Firstly, it guarantees an automatic parameter tuning mechanism, which is particularly beneficial in scenarios where manual parameter tuning could be challenging due to the complexity of the environment the robot operates in. Secondly, as the robot learns how to reach the goal, our approach eliminates the need for terminal cost, terminal constraint and a long prediction horizon to ensure successful navigation. Nevertheless, the reactive response of the *Low Road* must be complemented by the mediated response of the *High Road*, to be suitably implemented with slower but more articulated decision-making processes. To this aim, we are exploring large language models to interpret the robot operational scenario and provide contextual information to attain a trade-off between reactive responses and long-term strategic planning. The final proposed architecture could serve as a general purpose control framework, not limited to robot navigation. In fact, by integrating the NMPC as a brainstem that takes into account the kinematic model of the robot, the same architecture could be applied to any type of robot whose motion can be described by a kinematic model, such as manipulation tasks or industrial applications. In this context, the automatic tuning of NMPC's parameters performed by the amygdala and the integration of contextual and high-level information from the cerebral cortex would allow the robot to guarantee key characteristics such as precision, adaptability and safety during its operation.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Man and A. Damasio, "Homeostasis and soft robotics in the design of feeling machines," *Nature Machine Intelligence*, vol. 1, no. 10, pp. 446–452, 2019.
- [2] J.-M. Fellous, "From human emotions to robot emotions," *Architectures for Modeling Emotion: Cross-Disciplinary Foundations*, American Association for Artificial Intelligence, pp. 39–46, 2004.
- [3] C. P. Lee-Johnson and D. A. Carnegie, "Mobile robot navigation modulated by artificial emotions," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 469–480, 2009.
- [4] J. E. LeDoux, "Sensory systems and emotion: A model of affective processing," *Integrative psychiatry*, 1986.
- [5] E. T. Rolls, "Neurophysiology and functions of the primate amygdala." 1992.